

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Sapayeva Nazokat Shavkatovna

MINTAQADA IQTISODIY O'SISHNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH

YO'LLAR (XORAZM VILOYATI KESIMIDA)

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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